

**STABILITY OF THE QUADRATIC FUNCTIONAL EQUATIONS
IN THE CONTEXT OF 2-BANACH SPACES**

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ABSTRACT. The stability problem for functional equations have been extensively investigated by a number of mathematicians. During the last five decades, a number of research papers and research monographs have been published on various generalizations and applications of the Hyers-Ulam stability for several functional equations, and there are interesting results related to this problem. In this research article, we investigate the generalized Hyers-Ulam stability of the functional equation $f(2x+y)+f(x+2y) = 4f(x+y)+f(x)+f(y)$ in 2-Banach space, where $f : X \rightarrow X$.

1. Introduction

Stability of function for a function from normed space to Banach space has been studied by Hyers [9]. He has proved that for a function $f : X \rightarrow Y$, a function between normed space X and Banach space Y satisfying

$$\|f(x + y) - f(x) - f(y)\| \leq \delta$$

for each $x, y \in X$ and $\delta > 0$. Then there exists a unique additive function $T : X \rightarrow Y$ such that

$$\|f(x) - T(x)\| \leq \delta$$

for each $x \in X$. It is a positive answer to a problem raised by Ulam [16] for a functional equation on metric group. In fact several authors have studied the problem for different types of functional equations for functions from normed space to Banach space. (see [1, 2, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]). Stability of a functional equation for a function from a normed space to a 2-Banach space have been studied by B.M. Patel and A.B. Patel in [3], [4], [5].

Our aim is to study the stability of the functional equation

$$(1.1) \quad f(2x + y) + f(x + 2y) = 4f(x + y) + f(x) + f(y)$$

introduced by [7], for a function on normed space to 2-Banach space.

Definition 1.1. Let X and Y be real vector spaces, and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function. Then the functional equation

$$(1.2) \quad f(x + y) + f(x - y) = f(x) + f(y)$$

is said to be quadratic functional equation and every solution of the quadratic equation is said to be a quadratic function.

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Theorem 1.2. [7] *Let X and Y be real vector spaces. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ satisfies the functional equation (1.1) if and only if function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ satisfies the functional equation (1.2). Therefore, every solution of functional equation (1.1) is also a quadratic function.*

In the 1960s, S. Gähler introduced the concept of linear 2-normed spaces.

Definition 1.3. *Let X be a linear space over \mathbb{R} with $\dim X > 1$ and let $\|\cdot, \cdot\| : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function satisfying the following properties:*

- (1) $\|x, y\| = 0$ if and only if x and y are linearly dependent,
- (2) $\|x, y\| = \|y, x\|$,
- (3) $\|ax, y\| = |a|\|x, y\|$,
- (4) $\|x, y + z\| \leq \|x, y\| + \|x, z\|$

for each $x, y, z \in X$ and $a \in \mathbb{R}$. Then the function $\|\cdot, \cdot\|$ is called a 2-norm on X and $(X, \|\cdot, \cdot\|)$ is called a 2-normed space.

We introduce a basic property of 2-normed spaces as follows. Let $(X, \|\cdot, \cdot\|)$ be a linear 2-normed space, $x \in X$ and $\|x, y\| = 0$ for each $y \in X$. Suppose $x \neq 0$, since $\dim X > 1$, choose $y \in X$ such that $\{x, y\}$ is linearly independent so we have $\|x, y\| \neq 0$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, we have the following lemma.

Lemma 1.4. *Let $(X, \|\cdot, \cdot\|)$ be a 2-normed space. If $x \in X$ and $\|x, y\| = 0$, for each $y \in X$, then $x = 0$.*

Remark 1.5. *Let $(X, \|\cdot, \cdot\|)$ be a 2-normed space. Note that the conditions (2) and (4) imply that*

$$\|x + y, z\| \leq \|x, z\| + \|y, z\|$$

for each $x, y, z \in X$. Putting $w = x + y$, we get $\|w, z\| \leq \|x, z\| + \|w - x, z\|$, for each $x, y, z \in X$. So $\|w, z\| - \|x, z\| \leq \|w - x, z\|$, for each $x, z, w \in X$. Replacing w by x and x by w in the above inequality, we get $\|x, z\| - \|w, z\| \leq \|x - w, z\|$ for each $x, z, w \in X$. Thus, we have

$$(1.3) \quad \left| \|x, z\| - \|y, z\| \right| \leq \|x - y, z\|$$

for each $x, y, z \in X$. Hence the function $x \rightarrow \|x, y\|$ is continuous from X into \mathbb{R} for each fixed $y \in X$.

Let $(X, \|\cdot, \cdot\|)$ be a 2-normed space. For $x, z \in X$, let $p_z(x) = \|x, z\|$, $x \in X$. Then for each $z \in X$, p_z is a real-valued function on X such that $p_z(x) = \|x, z\| \geq 0$, $p_z(\alpha x) = |\alpha|\|x, z\| = |\alpha|p_z(x)$ and $p_z(x + y) = \|x + y, z\| = \|z, x + y\| \leq \|z, x\| + \|z, y\| = \|x, z\| + \|y, z\| = p_z(x) + p_z(y)$, for each $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ and all $x, y \in X$. Thus p_z is a semi-norm for each $z \in X$.

For $x \in X$, let $\|x, z\| = 0$, for each $z \in X$. By Lemma 1.4, $x = 0$. Thus for $0 \neq x \in X$, there is $z \in X$ such that $p_z(x) = \|x, z\| \neq 0$. Hence the family $\{p_z(x) : z \in X\}$ is a separating family of semi-norms.

Let $x_0 \in X$, for $\varepsilon > 0$, $z \in X$, let $U_{z,\varepsilon}(x_0) := \{x \in X : p_z(x - x_0) < \varepsilon\} = \{x \in X : \|x - x_0, z\| < \varepsilon\}$. Let $S(x_0) := \{U_{z,\varepsilon}(x_0) : \varepsilon > 0, z \in X\}$ and $\beta(x_0) := \{\cap \mathcal{F} : \mathcal{F} \text{ is a finite subcollection of } S(x_0)\}$. Define a topology τ on X by saying that a set U is open if for every $x \in U$, there is some $N \in \beta(x)$ such that $N \subset U$. That is, τ is the topology on X that has subbase $\{U_{z,\varepsilon}(x_0) : \varepsilon > 0, x_0 \in X, z \in X\}$. The topology τ on X makes X a topological

vector space. Since for $x \in X$ collection $\beta(x)$ is a local base whose members are convex, X is locally convex.

In the 1960s, S. Gähler and A. White introduced the concept of 2-Banach spaces.

Definition 1.6. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in a 2-normed space X is called a 2-Cauchy sequence if

$$\lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x_m, x\| = 0$$

for each $x \in X$

Definition 1.7. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in a 2-normed space X is called a 2-convergent sequence if there is an $x \in X$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x, y\| = 0$$

for each $y \in X$. If $\{x_n\}$ converges to x , we write $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = x$.

Definition 1.8. We say that a 2-normed space $(X, \|\cdot, \cdot\|)$ is a 2-Banach space if every 2-Cauchy sequence in X is 2-convergent in X .

Following shows that $\|\cdot, \cdot\|$ is continuous in each component.

Lemma 1.9. For a convergent sequence $\{x_n\}$ in a 2-normed space X ,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n, y\| = \|\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n, y\|$$

for each $y \in X$.

Proof. Since $\{x_n\}$ is a 2-convergent sequence in the 2-normed space X , there is an $x \in X$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x, y\| = 0$ for each $y \in X$. By (1.3), we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| \|x_n, y\| - \|x, y\| \right| \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x, y\| = 0$$

for each $y \in X$. Hence

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n, y\| = \|x, y\| = \|\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n, y\|$$

for each $y \in X$. □

2. Stability of a functional equation for functions $f : (X, \|\cdot, \cdot\|) \rightarrow (X, \|\cdot, \cdot\|)$

Throughout this section, consider X a real normed linear space. We also consider that there is a 2-norm on X which makes $(X, \|\cdot, \cdot\|)$ a 2-Banach space. For a function $f : (X, \|\cdot, \cdot\|) \rightarrow (X, \|\cdot, \cdot\|)$, define $D_f : X \times X \rightarrow X$ by

$$D_f(x, y) = f(2x + y) + f(x + 2y) - 4f(x + y) - f(x) - f(y)$$

for each $x, y \in X$.

Theorem 2.1. Let $\varepsilon \geq 0, 0 < p < 2, r > 0$. Assume that the function $f : X \rightarrow X$ satisfies

$$(2.1) \quad \|D_f(x, y), z\| \leq \varepsilon [\|x\|^p + \|y\|^p] \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, y, z \in X$. Then there exists a unique quadratic function $Q : X \rightarrow X$ satisfying (1.1) and

$$(2.2) \quad \|f(x) - Q(x), z\| \leq \frac{3\varepsilon}{9 - 3^p} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$.

Proof. Letting $x = y = 0$ in (2.1), we have $\|4f(0), z\| = 0$ for each $z \in X$, so we have $f(0) = 0$.

Putting $x = y$ in (2.1), we get

$$\|2f(3x) - 4f(2x) - 2f(x), z\| \leq 2\varepsilon\|x\|^p\|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore

$$(2.3) \quad \|f(3x) - 2f(2x) - f(x), z\| \leq \varepsilon\|x\|^p\|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Putting $y = 0$ in (2.1), we get

$$(2.4) \quad \|f(2x) - 4f(x), z\| \leq \varepsilon\|x\|^p\|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Multiplying (2.4) by 2, we get

$$(2.5) \quad \|2f(2x) - 8f(x), z\| \leq 2\varepsilon\|x\|^p\|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. By adding (2.3) and (2.5), we get

$$(2.6) \quad \|f(3x) - 9f(x), z\| \leq 3\varepsilon\|x\|^p\|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore

$$(2.7) \quad \left\| \frac{f(3x)}{9} - f(x), z \right\| \leq \frac{\varepsilon\|x\|^p\|z\|^r}{3}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Replacing x by $3x$ in (2.7), we get

$$(2.8) \quad \left\| \frac{f(9x)}{9} - f(3x), z \right\| \leq \frac{\varepsilon 3^p\|x\|^p\|z\|^r}{3}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. By (2.7) and (2.8), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \frac{f(9x)}{9^2} - f(x), z \right\| &\leq \left\| \frac{f(9x)}{9^2} - \frac{f(3x)}{9}, z \right\| + \left\| \frac{f(3x)}{9} - f(x), z \right\| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{9} \frac{\varepsilon 3^p\|x\|^p\|z\|^r}{3} + \frac{\varepsilon\|x\|^p\|z\|^r}{3} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon}{3} \left[1 + \frac{3^p}{9} \right] \|x\|^p\|z\|^r \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. By using induction on n , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| f(x) - \frac{1}{9^n} f(3^n x), z \right\| &\leq \frac{\varepsilon\|x\|^p\|z\|^r}{3} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{3^{pj}}{9^j} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon\|x\|^p\|z\|^r}{3} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} 3^{(p-2)j} \\ (2.9) \quad &= \frac{\varepsilon\|x\|^p\|z\|^r}{3} \left[\frac{1 - 3^{(p-2)n}}{1 - 3^{p-2}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. For $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \frac{1}{9^m} f(3^m x) - \frac{1}{9^n} f(3^n x), z \right\| &= \left\| \frac{1}{9^{m+n-n}} f(3^{m+n-n} x) - \frac{1}{9^n} f(3^n x), z \right\| \\ &= \frac{1}{9^n} \left\| \frac{1}{9^{m-n}} f(3^{m-n} \cdot 3^n x) - f(3^n x), z \right\| \\ &\leq \frac{\varepsilon \|3^n x\|^p \|z\|^r}{3 \cdot 9^n} \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} 3^{(p-2)j} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r}{3} 3^{(p-2)n} \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} 3^{(p-2)j} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r}{3} \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} 3^{(p-2)(n+j)} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r}{3} \frac{3^{(p-2)n} (1 - 3^{(p-2)(m-n)})}{1 - 3^{p-2}} \\ &\rightarrow 0 \text{ as } m, n \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore, $\{\frac{1}{9^n} f(3^n x)\}$ is a 2-Cauchy sequence in X , for each $x \in X$. Since X is a 2-Banach space, $\{\frac{1}{9^n} f(3^n x)\}$ 2-converges, for each $x \in X$. Define the function $Q : X \rightarrow X$ as

$$Q(x) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{9^n} f(3^n x)$$

for each $x \in X$. Now, from (2.9), we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\| f(x) - \frac{1}{9^n} f(3^n x), z \right\| \leq \frac{\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r}{3} \left[\frac{1}{1 - 3^{p-2}} \right]$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore

$$\|f(x) - Q(x), z\| \leq \frac{3\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r}{9 - 3^p}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Next we show that Q satisfies (1.1).

$$\begin{aligned} \|D_Q(x, y), z\| &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{9^n} \|D_f(3^n x, 3^n y), z\| \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\varepsilon}{9^n} (\|3^n x\|^p + \|3^n y\|^p) \|z\|^r \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \varepsilon [3^{(p-2)n} \|x\|^p + 3^{(p-2)n} \|y\|^q] \|z\|^r \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore $\|D_Q(x, y), z\| = 0$, for each $z \in X$. So we get $D_Q(x, y) = 0$. Next we prove the uniqueness of Q . Let Q' be another quadratic function satisfying (1.1) and (2.1). Since Q and Q' are quadratic, $Q(3^n x) = 9^n Q(x)$,

$Q'(3^n x) = 9^n Q'(x)$, for each $x \in X$.

$$\begin{aligned} \|Q(x) - Q'(x), z\| &= \frac{1}{9^n} \|Q(3^n x) - Q'(3^n x), z\| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{9^n} [\|Q(3^n x) - f(3^n x), z\| + \|f(3^n x) - Q'(3^n x), z\|] \\ &\leq \frac{1}{9^n} \frac{6\varepsilon \|3^n x\|^p \|z\|^r}{9 - 3^p} \\ &= 3^{(p-2)n} \frac{3\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r}{9 - 3^p} \\ &\longrightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore $\|Q(x) - Q'(x), z\| = 0$, for each $z \in X$. Therefore $Q(x) = Q'(x)$, for each $x \in X$. This proves the uniqueness of Q . \square

Theorem 2.2. Let $\varepsilon \geq 0, p > 2, r > 0$. Assume that the function $f : X \rightarrow X$ satisfies

$$(2.10) \quad \|D_f(x, y), z\| \leq \varepsilon [\|x\|^p + \|y\|^p] \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, y, z \in X$. Then there exists a unique quadratic function $Q : X \rightarrow X$ satisfying (1.1) and

$$(2.11) \quad \|f(x) - Q(x), z\| \leq \frac{3\varepsilon}{3^p - 9} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$.

Proof. By (2.6) of Theorem 2.1, we get

$$(2.12) \quad \|f(3x) - 9f(x), z\| \leq 3\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Replacing x by $\frac{x}{3}$ in (2.12), we get

$$(2.13) \quad \left\| f(x) - 9f\left(\frac{x}{3}\right), z \right\| \leq 3\varepsilon 3^{-p} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Replacing x by $\frac{x}{3}$ in (2.13), we get

$$(2.14) \quad \left\| f\left(\frac{x}{3}\right) - 9f\left(\frac{x}{9}\right), z \right\| \leq 3\varepsilon 3^{-2p} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Now, by (2.13) and (2.14)

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| f(x) - 9^2 f\left(\frac{x}{9}\right), z \right\| &\leq \left\| f(x) - 9f\left(\frac{x}{3}\right), z \right\| + \left\| 9f\left(\frac{x}{3}\right) - 9^2 f\left(\frac{x}{9}\right), z \right\| \\ &\leq 3\varepsilon 3^{-p} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r + 9 \cdot 3\varepsilon 3^{-p} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \\ &= 3\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r [3^{-p} + 9 \cdot 3^{-2p}] \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. By using induction on $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| f(x) - 9^n f\left(\frac{x}{3^n}\right), z \right\| &\leq 3\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} 3^{-p(j+1)} \cdot 9^j \\ &= 3\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} 3^{(-p+2)j-p} \\ (2.15) \quad &= 3\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \frac{3^{-p}(1 - 3^{(-p+2)n})}{1 - 3^{-p+2}} \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Now, for $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| 9^m f\left(\frac{x}{3^m}\right) - 9^n f\left(\frac{x}{3^n}\right), z \right\| &= \left\| 9^{m+n-n} f\left(\frac{x}{3^{m+n-n}}\right) - 9^n f\left(\frac{x}{3^n}\right), z \right\| \\ &= 9^n \left\| 9^{m-n} f\left(\frac{x}{3^{m-n} \cdot 3^n}\right) - f\left(\frac{x}{3^n}\right), z \right\| \\ &\leq 3\varepsilon 9^n \left\| \frac{x}{3^n} \right\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} 3^{(-p+2)j-p} \\ &= 3\varepsilon 3^{(-p+2)n} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} 3^{(-p+2)j-p} \\ &= 3\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} 3^{(-p+2)(n+j)-p} \\ &= 3\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \frac{3^{(-p+2)n} (1 - 3^{(-p+2)(m-n)})}{1 - 3^{-p+2}} \\ &\rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore $\left\{ 9^n f\left(\frac{x}{3^n}\right) \right\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . Since X is a 2-Banach space, $\left\{ 9^n f\left(\frac{x}{3^n}\right) \right\}$ converges in X . So, define $Q : X \rightarrow X$ as

$$Q(x) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} 9^n f\left(\frac{x}{3^n}\right)$$

for each $x \in X$. Now, by (2.15), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\| f(x) - 9^n f\left(\frac{x}{3^n}\right), z \right\| &\leq 3\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \frac{3^{-p}}{1 - 3^{-p+2}} \\ &= 3\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \frac{1}{3^p - 9} \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore

$$\|f(x) - Q(x), z\| \leq 3\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \frac{1}{3^p - 9}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. The rest of the proof is similar to the proof of Theorem 2.1. \square

Theorem 2.3. Let $\varepsilon \geq 0, 0 < p < 2$. Assume that the function $f : X \rightarrow X$ satisfies

$$(2.16) \quad \|D_f(x, y), z\| \leq \varepsilon [\|x\|^p + \|y\|^p] \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, y, z \in X$. Then there exists a unique quadratic function $Q : X \rightarrow X$ satisfying (1.1) and

$$(2.17) \quad \|f(x) - Q(x), z\| \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{4 - 2^p} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$.

Proof. By (2.4) of Theorem 2.1, we get

$$\|f(2x) - 4f(x), z\| \leq \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore

$$(2.18) \quad \left\| \frac{f(2x)}{4} - f(x), z \right\| \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Replacing x by $2x$ in (2.18), we get

$$(2.19) \quad \left\| \frac{f(4x)}{4} - f(2x), z \right\| \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{4} 2^p \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. By (2.18) and (2.19), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \frac{f(4x)}{4^2} - f(x), z \right\| &\leq \left\| \frac{f(4x)}{4^2} - \frac{f(2x)}{4}, z \right\| + \left\| \frac{f(2x)}{4} - f(x), z \right\| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{\varepsilon}{4} 2^p \|x\|^p \|z\|^r + \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \left[1 + \frac{2^p}{4} \right] \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Now, by using induction on $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \frac{f(2^n x)}{4^n} - f(x), z \right\| &\leq \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{2^{pj}}{4^j} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} 2^{(p-2)j} \\ (2.20) \quad &= \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \left[\frac{1 - 2^{(p-2)n}}{1 - 2^{p-2}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. For $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, by (2.20), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \frac{f(2^m x)}{4^m} - \frac{f(2^n x)}{4^n}, z \right\| &= \left\| \frac{f(2^{m+n-n} x)}{4^{m+n-n}} - \frac{f(2^n x)}{4^n}, z \right\| \\ &= \frac{1}{4^n} \left\| \frac{f(2^{m-n} \cdot 2^n x)}{4^{m-n}} - f(2^n x), z \right\| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{4^n} \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \|2^n x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} 2^{(p-2)j} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon}{4} 2^{(p-2)n} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} 2^{(p-2)j} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} 2^{(p-2)(n+j)} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon}{4} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \frac{2^{(p-2)n} (1 - 2^{(p-2)(m-n)})}{1 - 2^{p-2}} \\ &\rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore $\left\{ \frac{f(2^n x)}{4^n} \right\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . Since X is a 2-Banach space, $\left\{ \frac{f(2^n x)}{4^n} \right\}$ converges in X . So, define $Q : X \rightarrow X$ as

$$Q(x) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{4^n} f(2^n x)$$

for each $x \in X$. Now, by (2.20), we get

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\| \frac{f(2^n x)}{4^n} - f(x), z \right\| \leq \frac{\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r}{4(1 - 2^{p-2})}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore

$$\|Q(x) - f(x), z\| \leq \frac{\varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r}{4 - 2^p}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. The rest of the proof is similar to the proof of Theorem 2.1. \square

Theorem 2.4. Let $\varepsilon \geq 0, p > 2, r > 0$. Assume that a function $f : X \rightarrow X$ satisfies

$$(2.21) \quad \|D_f(x, y), z\| \leq \varepsilon [\|x\|^p + \|y\|^p] \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, y, z \in X$. Then there exists a unique quadratic function $Q : X \rightarrow X$ satisfying (1.1) and

$$(2.22) \quad \|f(x) - Q(x), z\| \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{2^p - 4} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$.

Proof. By (2.4) of Theorem 2.1, we get

$$\|f(2x) - 4f(x), z\| \leq \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore

$$(2.23) \quad \|f(2x) - 4f(x), z\| \leq \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Replacing x by $\frac{x}{2}$ in (2.23), we get

$$(2.24) \quad \left\| f(x) - 4f\left(\frac{x}{2}\right), z \right\| \leq \varepsilon 2^{-p} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Replacing x by $\frac{x}{2}$ in (2.24), we get

$$(2.25) \quad \left\| f\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) - 4f\left(\frac{x}{4}\right), z \right\| \leq \varepsilon 2^{-2p} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r$$

for each $x, z \in X$. By (2.24) and (2.25), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| f(x) - 16f\left(\frac{x}{4}\right), z \right\| &\leq \left\| f(x) - 4f\left(\frac{x}{2}\right), z \right\| + \left\| 4f\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) - 16f\left(\frac{x}{4}\right), z \right\| \\ &\leq \varepsilon 2^{-p} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r + 4\varepsilon 2^{-2p} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \\ &= \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r [2^{-p} + 4 \cdot 2^{-2p}] \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. By using induction on $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| f(x) - 4^n f\left(\frac{x}{2^n}\right), z \right\| &\leq \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} 2^{-p(j+1)} \cdot 4^j \\ &= \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} 2^{(-p+2)j-p} \\ (2.26) \quad &= \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \frac{2^{-p}(1 - 2^{(-p+2)n})}{1 - 2^{-p+2}} \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. For $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, $m > n$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| 4^m f\left(\frac{x}{2^m}\right) - 4^n f\left(\frac{x}{2^n}\right), z \right\| &= \left\| 4^{m+n-n} f\left(\frac{x}{2^{m+n-n}}\right) - 4^n f\left(\frac{x}{2^n}\right), z \right\| \\ &= 4^n \left\| 4^{m-n} f\left(\frac{x}{2^{m-n} \cdot 2^n}\right) - f\left(\frac{x}{2^n}\right), z \right\| \\ &\leq 4^n \varepsilon \left\| \frac{x}{2^n} \right\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} 2^{(-p+2)j-p} \\ &= \varepsilon 2^{(-p+2)n} \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} 2^{(-p+2)j-p} \\ &= \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} 2^{(-p+2)(n+j)-p} \\ &= \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \frac{2^{(-p+2)n-p} (1 - 2^{(-p+2)(m-n)})}{1 - 2^{(-p+2)}} \\ &\rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore $\left\{ 4^n f\left(\frac{x}{2^n}\right) \right\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . Since X is a 2-Banach space, $\left\{ 4^n f\left(\frac{x}{2^n}\right) \right\}$ converges in X . So, define $Q : X \rightarrow X$ as

$$Q(x) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} 4^n f\left(\frac{x}{2^n}\right)$$

for each $x \in X$. Now, by (2.26), we have

$$\left\| f(x) - 4^n f\left(\frac{x}{2^n}\right), z \right\| \leq \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \frac{2^{-p} (1 - 2^{(-p+2)n})}{1 - 2^{-p+2}}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\| f(x) - 4^n f\left(\frac{x}{2^n}\right), z \right\| &\leq \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \frac{2^{-p}}{1 - 2^{-p+2}} \\ &= \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \frac{1}{2^p - 4} \end{aligned}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. Therefore

$$\|f(x) - Q(x), z\| \leq \varepsilon \|x\|^p \|z\|^r \frac{1}{2^p - 4}$$

for each $x, z \in X$. The rest of the proof is similar to the proof of Theorem 2.1. \square

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